

CEPI | Brighton Collaboration

APPENDIX 3: ADULT INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Work Package: [WP10]

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DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Master Service Agreement	SPEAC 2.0	Service order	SO1
Project acronym	SPEAC	Full project title	Safety Platform for Emergency Vaccines
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CEPI Contract Manager	Dorota Zdanekwicz		

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Dissemination Level	Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Confidential <input type="checkbox"/>		

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

NAME OF DOCUMENT	DATE	VERSION	CONTRIBUTOR(S)	DESCRIPTION
Adult informed consent form	17-Sept-2024	V1.0	SPEAC Executive Board	Creation of the document

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[The adult ICF template and process should be adapted for special populations (e.g., minors, pregnant women, elderly patients lacking full capacity, migrants, prisoners) that require a tailored approach to consent, including possible surrogate decision-makers (e.g., parents, adult children) or study advocates (e.g., for inclusion of prisoners, orphans) and additional forms (e.g., assent forms), as well as tailoring to the details provided to participants during consent].

Participant information sheet

You are visiting this vaccination centre to receive the first dose of MPOX vaccine as part of routine care. This vaccination centre is participating in observational research to monitor the safety of COVID- 19 vaccines in [POPULATION OF INTEREST]. This study is taking place in [NUMBER] vaccination centres in [COUNTRY]. Around 10,000 persons vaccinated with mpox vaccine will be included in the study and followed up for 6 months after the last dose of mpox vaccine for specific health events of interest.

The study sponsor is [STUDY SPONSOR], and the principal investigators are [PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATORS].

If you participate in the study, data will be collected from you by interview at the time of enrolment and through regular questionnaires throughout the study period. By participating in the study you agree:

- to complete the study questionnaires [THOUGH MOBILE/WEBLINK/TELEPHONE] (weekly after each mpox vaccine dose, until 3 months after the second MPOX vaccine dose) (or more frequently if selected for the reactogenicity subset);
- to be contacted by phone in case of non-response, if no answer is received, your next of kin can be contacted;
- that the [NATIONAL AEFI FOCAL POINT/NATIONAL PHARMACOVIGILANCE CENTER, to be detailed in the protocol] may contact your healthcare provider if further investigation is required;
- that, in the event you learn you are pregnant during the study, the [NATIONAL AEFI FOCAL POINT/NATIONAL PHARMACOVIGILANCE CENTER, to be detailed in the protocol] may follow you until the time of delivery, to monitor the safety of mpox vaccines administered during pregnancy.

This study will not lead to any changes in your routine care. You will not be receiving any intervention (vaccine, drug, other) as part of the study. So, there will be no direct benefit to you from this research. However, information gathered from individuals vaccinated with MPOX vaccines will contribute to the safety surveillance of mpox vaccines.

Your individual identity will be protected because the final information used for the research study will not bear your name, contact details or any other personal information about you that will allow

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you to be identified. The vaccination centre will assign a responsible person to use and store the research data in a safe place.

The key-coded data obtained from this study will be stored in a secured database located in [COUNTRY]. Your personal data will always be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection and privacy laws. All information about you as an individual is confidentially and will be protected and only communicated to authorized persons. Any information collected from other physicians will be handled in the same confidential manner as those collected by the study doctor. Data will be archived for [XXX] years, as per national regulations, and will then be destroyed. Should you decide to withdraw from the study, data collected up until the time of the time of withdrawal will be used in the analyses.

If you are willing to participate in this study that will monitor the safety of MPOX vaccines, please sign and date this form. You are free to contact [XXX] to understand how your information will be used. If at any time you do not wish to share your information, you are free to contact [XXX] and withdraw from this study.

You also have the choice to say no and opt out of this research. Not participating, or withdrawing from this study, will not impact your access to healthcare.

I have read the above information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and all questions have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print name of participant

Signature of participant

Date _____

Day/month/year

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Statement by the researcher/person taking consent:

I have accurately read out the information sheet to the potential participant. I confirm that the participant was given every opportunity to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked by the participant have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this informed consent form has been provided to the participant.

Print name of researcher/person taking the consent _____

Signature of researcher/person taking the consent

Date _____

Day/month/year